

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1865	Alfred Rahlfs	1887	1887	1933		German Biblical scholar	1865-1935
1865	Charles Bally	1888	1889	1939		Swiss linguist	1865-1947
1865	Alexander Francis Chamberlain	1888	1911	1914		British-Canadian anthropologist	1865-1914
1865	Franz Skutsch	1888	1888	1912		German classical philologist and linguist	1865-1912
1865	Arthur Piaget	1888	1888	1938		Swiss historian, archivist and Romance philologist	1865-1952
1865	Sigmund Feist	1889		1935		German Jewish pedagogue and historical linguist	1865-1943
1865	Hermann Hirt	1889	1889	1936		German philologist and Indo-Europeanist	1865-1936
1865	August Fischer	1889	1989	1932		German orientalist	1865-1949
1865	Édouard Chavannes	1890		1918		French sinologist	1965-1918
1865	Wilhelm Bousset	1890	1890	1920		German theologian and New Testament scholar	1865-1920
1865	Walter Ewing Crum	1892		1937		British Scottish coptologist, or scholar in Coptic language and literature	1865-1944
1865	Carl Clemen	1892	1892	1933		German theologian and religious historian	1865-1940
1865	Jovan Cvijić	1893	1893	1927		Serbian geographer and ethnologist, president of the Serbian Royal Academy of Sciences and rector of the University of Belgrade	1865-1927
1865	James Henry Breasted	1894	1894	1927		American archaeologist, Egyptologist, and historian	1865-1935
1865	Dumitru Evolceanu	1894		1935		Romanian literary critic	1865-1938
1865	Paul Riessler	1899		1935		German orientalist, theologian and Bible translator	1865-1935
1865	Nicholas Marr	1901	1901	1934		Georgian historian and linguist	1865-1934
1865	Edgar Lee Hewett	1904	1904	1946		American archaeologist and anthropologist whose focus was the Native American communities of New Mexico and the southwestern United States	1865-1946
1866	Madeleine Colani	1914	1917	1929 w		French archaeologist (pioneering fieldworker who combined the roles of geologist, paleobotanist, archeologist, and ethnographer)	1866-1943
1866	George Fraser Black	1888	1894	1931		American (Scottish) librarian, historian and linguist	1866-1948
1866	Karl Sapper	1888	1900	1932		German traveller, explorer, antiquarian and linguist, who is known for his research into the natural history, cultures and languages of Central America around the turn of the 20th century	1866-1945

1866	Julius von Schlosser	1888	1888	1936	Austrian art historian and an important member of the Vienna School of Art History	1866-1938
1866	Paul Kretschmer	1889	1889	1936	German linguist who studied the earliest history and interrelations of the Indo-European languages and showed how they were influenced by non-Indo-European languages, such as Etruscan	1866-1956
1866	Louis Gauchat	1889	1890	1928	Swiss linguist	1866-1942
1866	Gilbert Murray	1889		1926	Australian-British classical scholar and public intellectual, with connections in many spheres	1866-1957
1866	Paul Clemen	1889	1889	1936	German art historian known in particular for his large inventory of monuments in the Rhineland area	1866-1947
1866	Charles Andler	1889	1889	1933	French Germanist and philosopher	1866-1933
1866	Max Margolis	1890	1891	1932	Lithuanian-American philologist	1866-1932
1866	Robert Ranulph Marett	1890	1913	1936	British ethnologist (anthropology of religion)	1866-1943
1866	Alfred Körte	1890	1890	1934	German classical philologist	1866-1946
1866	Johann Jakob Hess	1891	1891	1936	Swiss Egyptologist and Assyriologist and an expert in other Oriental languages	1866-1949
1866	Maurice Grammont	1892	1895	1939	French linguist	1866-1946
1866	Aby Warburg	1892	1892	1929	German art historian and cultural theorist who founded a private Library for Cultural Studies	1866-1929
1866	Gustav Adolf Deissmann	1892		1935	German biblical scholar	1866-1937
1866	Robert Priebsch	1893		1931	German professor and philologist	1866-1935
1866	Samuel Krauss	1893	1893	1938	Hungarian professor at the Jewish Teachers' Seminary	1866-1948
1866	Arthur Keith	1894	1894	1933	British Scottish anatomist and anthropologist, and a proponent of scientific racism	1866-1955
1866	Karl Vilhelm Zetterstéen	1895	1895	1931	Swedish orientalist	1866-1953
1866	Albert Tobias Clay	1896	No	1925	American professor, historian and Semitic linguist	1866-1925
1866	Alfredo Trombetti	1896		1929	Italian linguist	1866-1929
1866	Antoine Meillet	1897	1897	1927	French one of the most important French linguists of the early 20th century	1866-1936
1866	Clifford Herschel Moore	1897	1897	1931	American Latin scholar	1866-1931
1866	Jovan Hadži-Vasiljević	1898	1898	1948	Serbian historian, ethnographer, journalist and writer	1866-1948
1866	John Merlin Powis Smith	1899	1899	1932	British-American orientalist and biblical scholar	1866-1932
1866	Walter William Skeat	1900	No	1932	British English anthropologist	1866-1953

1866	Georg Friederici	1904	1906	1934	German ethnologist	1866-1947
1866	W. O. E. Oesterley	1908		1936	British Church of England theologian, and professor of Hebrew and Old Testament at King's College	1866-1950
1867	Horace Arthur Rose	1883	No	1918	British administrator in the Indian Civil Service and also an author of works related to India in the time of the British Raj	1867-1933
1867	Richard Heinze	1889	1889	1929	German classical philologist	1867-1929
1867	Franz Nikolaus Finck	1890		1910	German philologist	1867-1910
1867	Samuel Marinus Zwemer	1890	1904	1937	American (nicknamed The Apostle to Islam), missionary, traveler, and scholar	1867-1952
1867	Johannes Østrup	1890	1890	1935	Danish philologist and professor	1867-1938
1867	Max Jakob Friedländer	1891	1981	1939	German-Dutch museum curator and art historian	1867-1958
1867	Ludwig Radermacher	1891	1891	1937	German-Austrian classical philologist	1867-1952
1867	Friedrich Vollmer	1892	1892	1923	German classical philologist who specialized in Latin studies	1867-1923
1867	Paul Schwarz	1893	1893	1937	German orientalist, Iranist and Arabist	1867-1938
1867	Sten Konow	1893	1893	1937	Norwegian Indologist	1867-1948
1867	Franz Boll	1894	1894	1924	German Professor of Classical Philology	1867-1924
1867	Holger Pedersen	1895	1896	1953	Danish linguist	1867-1953
1867	Julius Ruska	1895	1895	1938	German orientalist, historian of science and educator	1867-1949
1867	Ernest Crawley	1895	No	1913	British schoolmaster, sexologist, anthropologist, sports journalist and exponent of ball games	1867-1924
1867	Vasilije Đerić	1895	1895	1928	Serbian historian and ethnographer	1867-1931
1867	John George Robertson	1895		1933	British Scottish philologist and professor of German language and literature	1867-1933
1867	Henry Stuart Jones	1895		1934	British academic and fellow of Trinity College	1867-1939
1867	William Craigie	1896		1936	British philologist and a lexicographer	1867-1957
1867	Frederick William Thomas	1897		1937	British English Indologist and Tibetologist	1867-1956
1867	Gertrude M. Godden	1897	No	1932 w	British author of works on anthropology and folklore	1867-1947
1867	Edmund Yard Robbins	1897	1910	1936	American the Ewing Professor of the Greek Language and Literature	1867-1942
1867	Eugène Pittard	1898	1898	1952	Swiss anthropologist	1867-1962
1867	Alexander Vasiliev	1898	1901	1938	Russian considered the foremost authority on Byzantine history and culture in the mid-20th century	1867-1953

1867	Edmond Doutté	1900		1926	French sociologist, orientalist and Islamologist - both Arabist and Berberologist - but also an explorer of Maghreb	1867-1926
1867	Inō Kanori	1900		1925	Japanese anthropologist, ethnologist, archaeologist and folklorist	1867-1925
1867	Marshall Howard Saville	1903		1932	American archaeologist, anthropologist	1867-1935
1867	Albert Buell Lewis	1906	1906	1940	American anthropologist to conduct a systematic, long-term field study in Melanesia	1867-1940
1868	Carl Brockelmann	1890	1890	1935	German Semiticist, foremost orientalist of his generation	1868-1956
1868	Georges Doutrepoint	1890	1890	1934	Belgian linguist, Walloon activist and academician	1868-1941
1868	K. B. Wiklund	1891	1896	1933	Swedish professor in Finno-Ugric languages	1868-1934
1868	Wilhelm Vöge	1891	1891	1916	German art historian, the " father of modern stylistic analysis " for medieval art	1868-1952
1868	John Dyneley Prince	1892	1892	1937	American linguist, diplomat, and politician	1868-1945
1868	Margaret Alford	1892		1943 w	British pioneering woman classicist who achieved a First at Cambridge University in 1887	1868-1951
1868	Carl Schmidt	1892	1892	1928	German Coptologist	1868-1938
1868	Pavle Popović	1893		1937	Serbian literary critic and historian, a professor and rector at the University of Belgrade	1868-1939
1868	Wilmer Cave Wright	1894	1895	1933 w	British-American classical philologist (culture and history of medicine)	1868-1951
1868	Northcote Whitridge Thomas	1894	1894	1928	British anthropologist and psychical researcher	1868-1936
1868	George Amos Dorsey	1894	1894	1915	American ethnographer of indigenous peoples of the Americas, with a special focus on the Caddoan and Siouan tribes of the Great Plains	1868-1931
1868	Helena Theresa Goessmann	1895	1895	1913 w	American lecturer, academic, and writer	1868-1926
1868	Anastas Ishirkov	1895	1895	1934	Bulgarian scientist, geographer and ethnographer	1868-1937
1868	Wilhelm Schmidt	1896		1948	Austrian roman catholic priest, scholar of religion, linguist, anthropologist, and ethnologist	1868-1954
1868	Louis Couturat	1896		1914	French logician, mathematician, philosopher, and linguist	1868-1914
1868	Émile Chassinat	1897		1948	French Egyptologist	1868-1948

1868	Eduard Norden	1898		1935	German classical philologist and historian of religion	1868-1941
1868	Joseph Anglade	1898	1905	1930	French philologist	1868-1930
1868	René Dussaud	1900		1932	French Orientalist, archaeologist, and epigrapher	1868-1958
1868	Reynold A. Nicholson	1900		1933	British eminent English orientalist, scholar of both Islamic literature and Islamic mysticism and widely regarded as one of the greatest Rumi (Mevlana or Mawlana) scholars and translators in the English language	1868-1945
1868	Clara Holst	1902	1903	1910 w	Norwegian philologist and women's rights pioneer	1868-1935
1868	François Bethune	1903		1938	Belgian Romanist and mediaevalist	1868-1938
1868	H. J. R. Murray	1906		1931	British educationalist, inspector of schools, and prominent chess historian	1868-1955
1868	Lida Shaw King	1907		1922 w	American classical scholar and college dean	1868-1932
1869	Maud Cunnington	1911	No	1947 w	British Welsh archaeologist, most famous for her pioneering work on the prehistoric sites of Salisbury Plain	1869-1951
1869	Louis de La Vallée-Poussin	1888	1888	1929	Belgian Indologist and scholar of Buddhist Studies	1869-1938
1869	Leonard William King	1890		1919	British archaeologist and Assyriologist	1869-1919
1869	William Allan Neilson	1891		1939	British Scottish-American educator, writer and lexicographer	1869-1946
1869	Aleš Hrdlička	1892		1942	Czech anthropologist	1869-1943
1869	Kurt Sethe	1892	1892	1934	German Egyptologist and philologist	1869-1934
1869	Eduard Hermann	1893	1893	1937	German linguist known for his comparative studies of Indo-European languages	1869-1950
1869	Richard Wünsch	1893	1893	1915	German classical philologist	1869-1915
1869	Alois Walde	1894	1894	1924	Austrian linguist	1869-1924
1869	Konrad Theodor Preuss	1894	1894	1934	German ethnologist	1869-1938
1869	John Myres	1894		1939	British archaeologist and academic, who conducted excavations in Cyprus in the late 19th and early 20th centuries	1869-1954
1869	Marjory Scott Wardrop	1894		1909 w	British English scholar and translator of Georgian literature	1869-1909
1869	August Heisenberg	1894	1894	1930	German Byzantinist	1869-1930

1869	Heinrich Lüders	1894	1894	1935	German Orientalist and Indologist known for his epigraphical analysis of the Sanskrit Turfan fragmentary manuscripts	1869-1943
1869	Robert Gregg Bury	1895	1910	1928	Irish clergyman, classicist, philologist, and a translator of the works of Plato and Sextus Empiricus into English	1869-1951
1869	Reginald Edward Enthoven	1896	No	1921	British administrator in the Indian Civil Service of the British Raj and an author of publications related to India	1869-1952
1869	Ramón Menéndez Pidal	1896		1968	Spanish philologist and historian	1869-1968
1869	Annie Marion MacLean	1897	1900	1925 w	American pioneering sociologist of the women's Chicago School, and is sometimes referred to as the "mother of contemporary ethnography"	1869-1934
1869	Constance Goddard DuBois	1897	No	1909 w	American novelist and an ethnographer	1869-1934
1869	Бартольд Василь	1898	1900	1930	Russian historian of German descent who specialized in the history of Islam and the Turkic peoples (Turkology)	1869-1930
1869	Albert Jenks	1899	1899	1936	American anthropologist (historical anthropological studies on rice cultivation,[2] the development of hominids,[3] and his identification of the skeletal remains of Minnesota Woman)	1869-1953
1869	Pliny Earle Goddard	1901	1904	1928	American linguist and ethnologist	1869-1928
1869	Charles Fossey	1902	No	1939	French assyriologist	1869-1946
1869	Wilhelm Heitmüller	1902	1902	1926	German Protestant theologian	1869-1926
1869	Richard Thurnwald	1906		1950	Austrian anthropologist and sociologist, known for his comparative studies of social institutions	1869-1954
1869	André Pirro	1907	1907	1937	French musicologist and an organist	1869-1943